

A Systematic Review of DDOS Attack Analysis Using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Method in Cyber security

Anita Bunker¹, Prof. Vijayta Raikwar²

1. M.TECH Student, Department of computer Science, Technocrat Institute of Technology, Bhopal
2. Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, Technocrat Institute of Technology, Bhopal

Abstract: Distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks are a significant cyber security risk and a danger to computer networks. The internet of things, or IOT, is a new era of information technology that makes it possible to connect devices to the internet, including smartphones, printers, smart watches, smart TVs, and cameras. However, as the internet expands, so do cyberattacks and the challenges associated with prioritizing deep learning and machine learning above cyber security. It is essential to create novel DDoS attack techniques as well as an efficient protection mechanism against these types of attacks. Recently, many attempts have been made to develop intelligent models to protect IoT networks against DDoS attacks. The main ongoing research issue is developing a model capable of protecting the network from DDoS attacks that is sensitive to various classes of DDoS and can recognize legitimate traffic to avoid false alarms. Subsequently, this study proposes combining three deep learning algorithms, namely recurrent neural network (RNN), long short-term memory (LSTM)-RNN, and convolutional neural network (CNN), to build a bidirectional CNN-BiLSTM DDoS detection model. The RNN, CNN, LSTM, and CNN-BiLSTM are implemented and tested to determine the most effective model against DDoS attacks that can accurately detect and distinguish DDoS from legitimate traffic. Study result indicates the ability of these models to perform in real-world IoT network systems. Papers representing each method were indexed, read, and summarized based on their temporal or thermal correlations. Because data are so important in ML/DL methods, we describe some of the commonly used network datasets used in ML/DL, discuss the challenges of using ML/DL for cybersecurity and provide suggestions for research directions. We have analyzed the relevant studies and categorized the results of the SLR into five areas: (i) The different types of DDoS attack detection in ML/DL approaches; (ii) the methodologies, strengths, and weaknesses of existing ML/DL approaches for DDoS attacks detection; (iii) benchmarked datasets and classes of attacks in datasets used in the existing literature; (iv) the preprocessing strategies, hyperparameter values, experimental setups, and performance metrics used in the existing literature; and (v) current research gaps and promising future directions.

Keywords: DDoS attack, DEEP learning, Machine Learning Cyber security intrusion Detection

I. Introduction

Distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks poses a serious threat to a wide range of industries, including the Internet of Things, smart cities, healthcare, information technology, and commercial parts [1]. Despite their scale, DDoS attacks continue to jeopardize the safety of networks of every sector of business due to their constant increases in complexity, volume, and frequency. Currently, there is a significant research gap on countering DDoS attacks, and even though defence mechanisms are becoming more effective, new forms of DDoS attacks may arise that current detection methods may not be able to adequately mitigate. For example, in 2019, Cambiasoet introduced the slow drop attack, which mimics the actions of a legitimate user [3].

There are still a number of shortcomings in the body of research on DDoS assaults and associated detection techniques, despite the many studies that have been done on the subject.

- Numerous studies concentrated on identifying DDoS attacks in particular domains, which limits the breadth and efficiency of these efforts.
- The significance of providing applicable datasets and their important properties that may be utilized to compare different detection algorithms side by side has been overlooked in certain studies [2]. The growing use of machine learning-based detection techniques makes it

more difficult for academics to contrast and assess various strategies.

- It can be challenging for readers to comprehend the techniques used by attackers in these attacks because certain studies have neglected to depict the most prevalent kinds of DDoS attacks.

II. Machine learning

plays a key part in the use of artificial intelligence and relates to robots' capacity to represent, process, and store information in order to learn from vast amounts of data[4]. With the emergence of numerous new fields, machine learning has recently experienced tremendous, previously unheard-of appeal. Big data analysis has given previously established study topics fresh impetus. Artificial intelligence has been made possible by machine learning techniques thanks to the enormous increase in the amount of digital data, the accessibility of computing resources, and the development of optimization algorithms [5]. For example, a lot of medical data is evaluated to help with diagnosis and therapy. By analyzing the medical data, machine learning systems identify trends in the bio-signals. They propel progress in medical research and treatment.

Current machine learning algorithm research aims to address the following problems:

- Creating algorithms for machine learning that can handle big amounts of information with labels computationally

and creating algorithms that don't require a lot of data [6].

- creating resource-efficient machine learning algorithms and creating a means for protecting privacy for a range of uses [7].

III. DDoS Attacks

An online network or service is at risk of security from DDoS attacks. In this thesis, we address DDoS attacks as our research challenge and offer several frameworks for potential solutions. By depleting the network or computational assets accessible to traffic or computation/processing, DDoS assaults seek to reduce the accessibility of a service by preventing authorized users from accessing the victims' services [8].

IV. Launching a DDoS

A DDoS assault can be initiated in a variety of ways, but the most typical method is for an attacker to flood a victim server with packets. Important resources are used up in this way, making it harder for authorized users to access them. Sending a few erroneous packets that cause the victim systems to reboot or freeze is another popular strategy. Subverting machines on a victim network and consuming important resources is another approach to deny a service [9]. This prevents the same network from being available for either internal or external services. Such attacks can be carried out in a variety of methods, are hard to anticipate, and are only found after the fact.

There are four primary actors in a DDoS assault: the attacker, the controller, the zombies, and the victim. The attack unfolds out in multiple phases [10]. An attacker looks for open ports on a remotely accessible workstation in order to initiate an assault. After the vulnerability is identified, the attacker sends malicious malware that replicates and initiates the attack on the machine being targeted when it is executed [11]. Disguising the malware as a genuine internet packet for instance, by sending it as a file attached in an email is another method of malware dissemination. An attacker can remotely control all of this. Spoofing is used to impede attack detection and characterization, excluding reflection attacks, to stop agent machines from being discovered [12].

Figure 1. Example of DDoS attacks [29]

V. Types of DDoS Attacks

Volume-based assaults, Protocol assaults, and Application layer assaults are the three categories under which DDoS attacks fall. Attacks based on volume are carried out by directly overloading a victim's server with packets of Internet traffic. UDP flooding, ICMP flooding, and spoofing packet flooding can all do this [13]. Ping of Death, fragmented packets, and SYN flooding are examples of protocol-based attacks. Protocol attacks raise the traffic burden on the server and use up its Internet resources. Attacks at the application layer, such as GET/POST Floods, focus on particular weaknesses in security protocols. Here is a description of an example assault for each type [14].

5.1. UDP flood attack

Unlike Transmission Control Protocol (TCP), User Datagram Protocol (UDP) sends packets straight to the target server without a handshake. Using this protocol property, the attacker sends a lot of traffic, using up all of the target server's network resources in the process [15].

5.2. SYN flood

In the TCP protocol, a connection is formed via a three-way handshake in which the client and server exchange acknowledgement (ACK) and synchronization (SYN) messages. SYN attacks occur when a client sends an incorrect ACK message with a faked IP address in response to a server. In response to an incorrect IP address Synchronize (SYN) message, the server responds and then waits for a response from the client [16]. The connection does not serve a legitimate user during this wait period; instead, it is idle.

5.3. Ping of Death

Ping of Death (POD) is a dated form of a ping flood attack using the Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) [17]. The maximum packet size allowed by the IP protocol to be exchanged between two devices is 65,535 bytes for IPv4. An unpatched system may suffer greatly if faulty or large packets are sent using the straightforward ping command [18].

5.4. Denial of Sleep Attack

The Media Access Control (MAC) layer protocol is crucial for regulating and conserving power usage in wireless sensor nodes [19]. When an attacker gains knowledge of the MAC protocol, they can circumvent authentication and encryption procedures, leading to a denial of sleep assault [20].

VI. Machine Learning Approaches

The majority of research has depended on machine learning techniques, such as prediction, clustering, and classification. Song and Liu provide a real-time detection system that makes use of Storm, a distribution system, and a dynamic algorithm. They take into account three factors in their suggested solution: the maturity of large data processing technology, analysis technology, and real-time data feedback [21]. But the primary focus of their solution is a mobile network traffic dataset. Their results indicate strong performance. On the other hand, contrasting the outcomes of various algorithms and datasets might be intriguing. In order

to combat DDoS flooding attacks, Hammed and Ali suggest a DDoS detection system that use the counter base algorithm run via Hadoop technology. However, they are unable to achieve effective processing delays in their investigation [22].

Jiangtao and colleagues [19] present a detection technique that combines several multi-classifiers with Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). They contend that creating several classifiers yields more accurate results than using static classifiers [23]. Analyzing their method's performance on a huge dataset would be fascinating. Comparing their findings to those obtained with the K-Nearest Neighbours (K-NN) algorithm, they demonstrate an improvement in performance [24].

M Zekri et al. [35] analyze the CETS and suggest a DDoS attack detection method utilizing an Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) classification technique. The method is verified by calculating the highest Lyapunov exponent. When compared to other techniques, their results demonstrate high detection rates. To determine the effect, it has on their performance and detection time, it would be intriguing to take into account additional information contained in packets (i.e., features/fields) and apply their technique in a distributed system.

In order to differentiate between DDoS attack traffic and flash crowds, Y. Liu et al. [40] suggest using an entropy variations approach to categorize Internet traffic. To increase detection accuracy, they employ distributed Internet threat, fuzzy logic for the dynamic selection of classification algorithms, and a Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) environment for processing massive amounts of data for training.

VII. Deep Learning Approaches

The body of research on deep learning techniques has expanded quickly recently. Kim et al. provide a deep learning-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) model. They make use of the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) architecture with Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). Following model construction, their evaluation findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the deep learning approach for IDS utilizing the metrics of Detection Rates (DR) and False Alarm Rate (FAR) [25].

For Net-Work Intrusion Detection (NIDS), Mohammad Najafimehr et al. (2023) [18] compares and assess three popular deep learning models: a basic Deep Neural Network (DNN), Self-Taught Learning (STL), and RNN, which is built on both LSTM and Auto encoder. The accuracy and precision of the algorithms are the main points of evaluation. They state that the LSTM model only achieves 79.2% accuracy, whereas the auto encoder achieves 98.9% accuracy. As a result, they advise that additional hyperparameter adjustment will probably be needed to raise the LSTM model's accuracy. Nevertheless, they come to the conclusion that for NIDS, the Auto encoder deep learning method performs better than other models.

A DNN model is proposed and constructed for Software Defined Networking (SDN) by Sheeraz Ahmed et al. (2023). They affirm that flow-based anomaly detection in SDN settings can benefit greatly from the application of deep learning techniques. They use a confusion matrix to assess the system's performance and compare the outcomes to those of other comparable methods. Despite using only six features from the dataset, they assert that the DNN approach offers a promising

level of accuracy and can be generalized.

Figure 2. Framework of DDoS attack detection system based on ML/DL [24]

VIII. Methodology to Be Employed

Current research takes into account the secondary data analysis method which is better known as Exploratory research. This paper critically analyses several ML/DL based techniques & algorithms & their comparative advantages & disadvantages. This section details the procedure and implementation of deep learning detection based on topological and flow features. As shown in Figure 1, our proposed DDoS detection system has three main parts [26]. The first part is the extraction module. It is responsible for extracting features from public datasets or actual scenes and transforming samples into graph data consisting of nodes and edges. The second part is the training module, which builds a classification model that can mine deep-level information from samples. The input is sample data, the output is label type, and parameters are optimized during training. The third part is the evaluation module, which compares detection effects under different hyperparameters to select the optimal configuration [27]. When the above stages are completed, the pattern analysis for feature extraction is saved as an extractor, and the trained neural network is preserved as a classifier. Then, real traffic can be quickly classified by running through these processing parts only once without retraining.

IX. Related work

Mahmood A. Al-Shareeda et al. (2023) Distributed denial of service (DDoS) assaults pose a severe danger to internet security. A denial-of-service attack (DDoS) aims to stop legitimate users from utilizing a service by sending a massive number of messages or requests to the central server, overloading it to the point of failure. This attack is dangerous because it relies on a large number of bots that are controlled (infected) by a single botmaster using a fictitious IP address. It also requires little effort or extra tools. This paper will go over some machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) strategies for detecting and assessing DDoS attacks. To help decide when to employ which of these techniques, this study also compares and analyzes the important differences between ML and DL techniques.

Figure 3. Overview of Literature Survey Protocol [15]

Distributed denial of service (DDoS) assaults is becoming a more serious danger to organizations and governmental institutions, according to Sheeraz Ahmed et al. (2023). They hurt company branding, restrict access to information and services, and hurt online companies (Fig. 3 presents various stages for review of literature). Because they mimic real users, attackers deploy application layer DDoS attacks, which are difficult to identify. We analyze the properties of incoming packets, such as the size of HTTP frame packets, the number of Internet Protocol (IP) addresses sent, port mappings that are constant, and the number of IP addresses utilizing proxy IP, in order to combat unique application layer DDoS attacks in this study. Using standard datasets, the CTU-13 dataset, real weblogs (dataset) from our organization, and experimentally constructed datasets from DDoS attack tools (Slow Lairs, Hulk, Golden Eyes, and Xerex), we examined client behavior in public attacks. Metrics-based attack detection is assessed using a deep learning method called a multilayer perceptron (MLP). The suggested MLP classification system has a 98.99% detection efficiency for DDoS attacks, according to simulation findings. In comparison to conventional classifiers such as Naïve Bayes, Decision Stump, Logistic Model Tree, Naïve Bayes Updateable, Naïve Bayes Multinomial Text, AdaBoostM1, Attribute Selected Classifier, Iterative Classifier, and OneR, our suggested technique yielded the lowest value of false positives, at 2.11%.

Figure 4. Generalized DDoS attack systems employing Machine Learning & Deep Learning Methods [11]

Distributed denial of service (DDoS) (Fig. 4) assaults is a serious cybersecurity threat to computer networks, according to Mohammad Najafimehr et al. (2023). Creating a strong defence against these attacks is essential, but difficult because of the variety of attack methods, heterogeneity of networks and computing platforms, and intricate communication protocols. Furthermore, the development of novel DDoS attack techniques poses a serious risk to the effectiveness of current defences. Numerous machine learning approaches have demonstrated potential in identifying DDoS assaults with high detection rates and low false-positive rates. This survey study provides a thorough taxonomy of machine learning-based techniques for identifying DDoS attacks, as well as an analysis of the associated difficulties and a discussion of supervised, unsupervised, and hybrid approaches. up addition, we examine pertinent datasets, stressing their advantages and disadvantages, and suggest avenues for future study to fill up the gaps in this field. The purpose of this paper is to give readers a thorough grasp of DDoS attack detection mechanisms so that academics and practitioners can create cybersecurity defences against these types of attacks. Because DDoS attacks are multifaceted and a serious threat to computer networks, this research is crucial because several machine learning algorithms have demonstrated promise in identifying them. Among its ramifications are insights that can guide the creation of strong defences against DDoS attacks.

İsa Avel et al. (2023) The Internet of Things (IoT) in smart buildings is expanding at a rapid rate, which makes it necessary to continuously assess potential dangers and their consequences. Innovative solutions are required since traditional techniques are becoming less and less effective at assessing risk and reducing related hazards. IoT cybersecurity solutions are essential for many facets of daily life, not just Building Management System (BMS) applications. assaults using botnets to perform Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) (Fig. 4) assaults against key BMS software can seriously jeopardize assets and user safety. In this research, we offer a novel technique that combines the support vector machine (SVM) algorithm, an artificial neural network (ANN) predictor, and the Slime Mould Optimization technique (SMOA) for feature selection. In the context of BMS, our improved algorithm estimates DDoS attack risk variables with an exceptional accuracy of 97.44%. It also demonstrates an astounding 99.19% accuracy rate in anticipating DDoS attacks, thereby averting system interruptions, and handling cyber threats. We do a comparative analysis with the K-Nearest Neighbour Classifier (KNN), which produces an accuracy rate of 96.46%, in order to further validate our work. The Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity (CIC) IoT Dataset 2022 is used to train our model, which allows for behavioural analysis and vulnerability testing on a variety of IoT devices using several protocols, including IEEE 802.11, Zigbee-based, and Z-Wave.

Figure 5. DDoS attack system Taxonomy on the basis of ML/DL [23]

In comparison to traditional networks, software-defined networking, or SDN, offers programmability, manageability, flexibility, and efficiency (Naziya Aslam et al., 2024). These result from the control and data planes of an SDN being separated or operating independently of one another. The centralized structure of SDN and the decoupling of two planes improve defence against DDoS attacks by making it simpler to set network device regulations. The controller's global network view is responsible for its capacity to filter network traffic and identify harmful flows. Although the separation of the control and data planes had many advantages, it also presented a new difficulty because of its vulnerability to DDoS attacks. One of the biggest risks to SDN is DDoS attacks, in which the attacker interferes with ordinary users' services. When it comes to detecting DDoS attacks, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have proven to be superior to statistical or policy-based approaches. A comprehensive taxonomy of DDoS defence systems has been developed by us. 132 of the 260 research articles that we surveyed focused on ML- and/or DL-based methods for detecting DDoS attacks in SDN. We go over the previous studies that have used feature selection algorithms on the dataset to identify the most useful and ideal attributes for DDoS attack detection. We showcase the characteristics of many publicly accessible DDoS datasets. Additionally, we make the case that feature selection techniques should be used after SDN-specific datasets have been created in order to improve DDoS attack detection. In conclusion, we outline the research issues related to SDN security that may aid future studies and the creation of fresh approaches to SDN security.

Distributed Denial of Service Attacks are currently the most dangerous cyber threat, according to Kimmi Kumari et al. (2022). The impacted server slows down its resources, such bandwidth and buffer size, by making it more difficult for it to serve legitimate clients. This work proposes a mathematical model for distributed denial-of-service attacks. To identify assaults and typical situations, machine learning algorithms like Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes are employed. The experimental study makes use of the CAIDA 2007 Dataset. This dataset is used to test and train machine learning algorithms, and the results validate the learned algorithms. The Weka data mining platform is employed in

this investigation, and the outcomes are analyzed and contrasted. The current study is contrasted with alternative machine learning methods utilized in relation to denial-of-service attacks.

Sharmin Aktar et al. (2023) Various network assaults have been on the rise lately as a result of the cyber world's widespread use and expansion. One of the most dangerous dangers to the Internet today is the distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) assault, in which the attacker bombards the target system with enormous volumes of packets in an attempt to prevent authorized users from accessing online services. To protect against these threats, accurate attack detection measurement is essential. In order to identify abnormalities, a contractive autoencoder-based deep learning model is proposed in this research. Using the compacted representation of the input data, we train our model to identify the typical traffic pattern. To identify the attack, we subsequently employ a stochastic threshold technique. CIC-IDS2017, NSL-KDD, and CIC-DDoS2019 are three well-known intrusion detection system datasets that were used in the evaluation process. To demonstrate the effectiveness of our model, we have compared the outcomes with those of a simple autoencoder and various deep learning techniques. Our findings show that the suggested method successfully detected intrusions on the CIC-DDoS2019 dataset, with an accuracy ranging from 93.41% to 97.58%. Furthermore, using the NSL-KDD and CIC-IDS2017 datasets, it obtained accuracy rates of 96.08% and 92.45%, respectively.

Software-defined networking (SDN), according to Bahashwan AA et al. (2023), is a ground-breaking advancement in network technology with a number of appealing advantages, such as flexibility and manageability. Notwithstanding these benefits, distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks can compromise SDN, and because of the damage they can cause to the SDN network, they pose a serious risk. Even with a variety of security techniques, DDoS attack detection is still an open research problem. In order to methodically examine and critically evaluate the current DDoS attack strategies based on machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), or hybrid approaches published between 2014 and 2022, this study offers a systematic literature review (SLR). To thoroughly cover pertinent studies, we used eight internet databases and a predetermined SLR technique, which we followed in two steps. Seventy studies are recognized as definite primary research after two steps of automatic and manual searching. The trend suggests that over the past few years, there has been a significant increase in the number of studies on SDN DDoS attacks. The investigation revealed that single, hybrid, and ensemble ML-DL are the main methods used in the detection techniques now in use. To test those methodologies, private generated datasets are most commonly utilized, followed by unrealistic datasets. Furthermore, the review makes the case that further attention is needed to address the unresolved problems and unanswered questions raised in this SLR because of the paucity of available material.

According to Devrim Akgun et al. (2022), when communicating across a network, data is subject to several threats. Finding network communication intrusions is becoming more and more important. Researchers create efficient intrusion detection systems by using machine learning techniques. In this work, we suggested an intrusion

detection system that detects DDoS attacks using a deep learning model and preprocessing steps. In order to do this, a number of models built on Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), and Deep Neural Networks (DNN) have been assessed for real-time and detection performance. We used the CIC-DDoS2019 dataset, which is widely used in the literature, to test the proposed model. To the CIC-DDoS2019 dataset, we used preprocessing methods such feature removal, random subset selection, feature selection, duplication removal, and normalization. Better recognition performance was thus attained for the testing and training assessments. The CNN-based inception-like model produced the best results among the suggested models, with 99.99% for binary and 99.30% for multiclass accuracy, according to the test findings. In addition, the suggested model's inference time appears promising for different test data sizes when compared to baseline models with less trainable parameters. When compared to state-of-the-art investigations, the suggested IDS system and the preprocessing techniques yield superior results.

Sidra Abbas et al. (2024) The Internet of Things (IoT) is a rapidly emerging technology that has great promise for addressing various societal issues. It is expected to play a major role in the future. The ability to control and monitor physical items via the Internet forms the basis of the Internet of Things. Because more aspects of the IoT network architecture can be accessed online, it is more susceptible to attackers and hackers. The intricacy of cyberattacks has increased, making both public and private sector entities more vulnerable. They damage company branding, jeopardize Internet operations, and impose restrictions on data and facility access. Because machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have so much potential across a wide range of fields, businesses and academics are thinking about utilizing them to prevent cyberattacks. A number of deep learning techniques are applied to extract different patterns from numerous annotated datasets. When it comes to identifying cyberattacks, DL is a useful technique. Thus, it is now more important than ever to separate and detect network data early in order to mitigate intrusions. The study uses a variety of deep-learning model types, such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and deep neural networks (DNNs), to detect cyberattacks on various network traffic streams. The effectiveness of the suggested strategy is evaluated using the CICIoT2023 dataset from the Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity. Data preprocessing, reliable scalar and label encoding methods for categorical variables, and deep learning models for model prediction are all included in the suggested approach. The results of the experiment show that the RNN model had the highest accuracy, at 96.56%. According to the test results, the suggested strategy for spotting cyberattacks in a real-world Internet of Things environment is more effective than alternative approaches.

Meenakshi Mittal et al. (2022): Technology is becoming an essential aspect of living in the modern world. In actuality, everything has moved from offline to online during the Covid-19 pandemic, including businesses and educational institutions. As a result, attacks and incursions using Internet-based technology proliferate exponentially. The Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assault is a deadly danger that can quickly bring down Internet-based services and applications.

Because the attackers are always changing their skill techniques, they manage to avoid detection by the current systems. The amount of data created and stored has multiplied, making it impossible for conventional detection techniques to identify new DDoS attacks. In order to detect DDoS, this study thoroughly explores the important literature, particularly in the field of deep learning. For the purpose of looking for contemporary literature, the writers have investigated four widely used digital libraries (IEEE, ACM, ScienceDirect, and Springer) as well as one academic search engine (Google Scholar). After a thorough analysis of pertinent literature, the results of the SLR were divided into five main research areas: (i) the various deep learning approaches for detecting DDoS attacks; (ii) the approaches, advantages, and disadvantages of these approaches; (iii) benchmarked datasets and attack classes in the datasets used in the literature; and (iv) the preprocessing strategies, hyperparameter values, experimental setups, and performance metrics used in the literature.

There are further difficulties with distributed cloud computing and its reliance on internet access, according to Marram Amitha et al. (2023). As per the cloud service providers, these assets provide a great deal of flexibility and may be accessed via the Internet utilizing commonly used formats, protocols, and needs for networking. assaults that seriously damage the cloud and reduce its performance are common, and include distributed denial of service assaults. Firewalls and other conventional methods of detection are not effective in identifying internal threats. Because of the growing volume of data generated and stored, attackers regularly alter their skill schemes, making it difficult for traditional detection tools to spot new DDoS attacks [28]. Artificial neural networks of the radial basis function (RBF) type are frequently employed for problems involving function approximation, pattern recognition, and classification. They are not commonly employed directly within convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) detection, despite their use in a variety of domains. In order to improve the overall security of cloud computing infrastructures, this research provides a hybrid model of Radial Basis Function (RBF) and LSTM networks-based technique for DDoS attack detection and mitigation. The efficacy of our suggested approach in detecting DDoS attacks and lessening their effects on cloud systems is assessed using the benchmark dataset CICDDoS2019.

According to Li Xinlong et al. (2022), a Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack happens when a network or server receives a high volume of traffic directed at it from hundreds, thousands, or even millions of other computers with the intention of crashing the system and interfering with its operation. These kinds of attacks are frequently used to momentarily stop websites or applications. It is frequently necessary to use models that can handle the time information present in network traffic flows to solve such issues. Using any dependencies between the various components of a data stream, we employ a Hybrid Deep Learning technique in this study to detect fraudulent web traffic in the form of DDoS attacks, managing the web flow of information reaching a server. A novel and state-of-the-art hybrid Hierarchical Temporal Memory (HTM) model has been put forth [29]. This model's functioning is mostly based on the neocortex, a region of the cerebral cortex. The perception of senses,

language understanding, and motor control are among the basic brain activities that are controlled by the neocortex. An LSTM shell is added to the hybrid implementation in order to enable it to encode time sequences that include incoming data.

Rao, G. S. et al. (2023) DoS attacks are a serious problem for network security. Computer networks and the internet are indispensable to our day-to-day activities and enterprises. Harmful acts have increased in tandem with our reliance on technology and communication networks. Modern communication is plagued by network dangers. Network traffic flow needs to be watched out for malicious behavior and attacks in order to maintain networks operating efficiently and users' data secure. Attacks known as denial-of-service (DoS) are designed to take down a website, web service, or network server. DDoS and DoS attacks can target computer networks and services. Maybe the easiest DDoS attack is flooding. DDoS attacks send enormous volumes of pointless data to a site or network. The goal of the study is to secure the network, preserve service continuity, and fortify network infrastructures against various attacks. Attacks known as denial-of-service (DoS) block the access and usage of information systems and resources by authorized users. Details illustrate DoS/DDoS assaults with UDP, ICMP, and the more common TCP flood attacks. These strikes need to be identified right away and terminated. During COVID-19, schools and businesses went online [30]. Traditional Machine Learning-based DoS/DDoS attack detection techniques are ineffective due to the massive amount of data that is generated and kept. SVM, MLP, and LSTM algorithms are used in this work for deep learning. The Deep Learning model that has been suggested can differentiate between network attack activity and regular traffic by learning and constructing binary and multiclass classification models. We search traffic patterns and data for anomalies and attack signals. Our deep learning model is thoroughly and precisely examined. During detection, the system looks for routine network data or attacks. This model finds things 97% of the time with the use of the MLP Algorithm. Performance comparison of the proposed system is done using LSVM ML classification. The topic of this essay is traffic behavior. Traffic filtering was also used in this investigation to get rid of suspicious or attack-signature traffic. Next, we used rate-limiting to restrict traffic coming from designated sources and places. Network packet data is captured for analysis and repair using Linux Sniffer and Python SCAPY. compared the analysis and mitigation of packet capture using Scapy and Wireshark. The study looks at how to prevent network DoS/DDoS attacks. These methods identify and counteract flood-related denial-of-service attacks to maintain network security and system functionality. You have to constantly research and create new strategies in order to stay on top of DoS attacks and the threat landscape.

Tennakoon C. et al. (2022) Distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks are a significant danger in the field of cybersecurity because they can interfere with legitimate users' access to online services, thereby affecting their availability. The potential financial ramifications of such attacks are enormous, as the high availability of internet services is essential to their operation. Due to attackers' ability to constantly innovate and uncover flaws in intrusion detection models or mitigation measures, the intensity of

DDoS attacks is on the rise. The history of DDoS attacks shows that the attackers initially targeted the network and transport layers of the OSI model. However, more recent history in the cybersecurity field demonstrates that the attack momentum has shifted toward the application layer of the OSI model, which makes it difficult to distinguish between malicious and benign traffic, making application-layer DDoS attack defence a complex task. Any DDoS detection technique must aim for high accuracy with high DDoS classification recall in order to maintain the system's dependability and credibility. This research proposes a deep learning strategy for application-layer DDoS detection using deep neural networks for attack categorization and autoencoders for feature selection. The most attractive elements from the packet flows are extracted, and the result is a popular benchmark dataset called CIC DoS 2017. The suggested model has the highest accuracy rate among the literature that has been evaluated thus far, achieving 99.83% accuracy with a detection rate of 99.84% while retaining a false-negative rate of 0.17%.

According to Wei Guo et al. (2022), the first line of defence against distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks, which are the most prevalent type of hack against infrastructure, is detection. To increase categorization performance, the present DDoS detection mostly leverages machine learning and deep learning techniques, either combined or improved. Topological connection changes are not taken into account when training classifiers, as most of them rely solely on statistical flow features. This one-sidedness reduces the accuracy of detection and makes it impossible to distribute attack sources for the deployment of defences. In this work, we propose a topological and flow feature-based deep learning method (GLD-Net) that utilizes graph attention network (GAT) to mine correlations between non-Euclidean features to fuse flow and topological features while simultaneously extracting flow and topological features from time-series flow data. The node neighbourhood relationship is obtained by the long short-term memory (LSTM) network connected behind GAT, and feature dimension reduction and traffic type mapping are accomplished by using the fully connected layer. The GLD-Net method's detection accuracy for two classifications (normal and DDoS flow) and three classifications (normal, rapid DDoS flow, and slow DDoS flow) is 0.993 and 0.942, respectively, according to experiments conducted on the NSL-KDD2009 and CIC-IDS2017 datasets. Its average improvement over the current DDoS attack detection systems is 0.11 and 0.081, respectively. Furthermore, the attack source distribution can be inferred based on the correlation coefficient, which varies from 0.7 to 0.83 between the attack flow detection accuracy and the four source distribution indicators. Notably, we are the first to apply graph-style neural networks to combine topology and flow data and accomplish high-performance DDoS attack intrusion detection. The development of network security solutions in other sectors and related research will be significantly impacted by the findings of this study.

Najafimehr, M. et al. (2022) Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assaults are becoming a more frequent danger to computer networks, where service availability is essential. A popular and promising method for detecting DDoS attacks that produces good results for known attacks is machine learning (ML). They nearly never identify malicious traffic

that is unknown to them, though. In this research, a novel approach that combines supervised and unsupervised algorithms is proposed. Using a number of flow-based criteria, a clustering algorithm first distinguishes the abnormal traffic from the regular data. The clusters are then labelled using a classification algorithm and specific statistical criteria. We assess the suggested approach using a big data processing framework by testing on an alternative set of assaults from the more recent CICDDoS2019 dataset and training on the CICIDS2017 dataset. The outcomes show that, in comparison to the ML classification methods, our method's Positive Likelihood Ratio (LR+) is almost 198% greater.

Distributed denial-of-service assaults, or DDoS attacks, are among the most prevalent types of network attacks that occur nowadays (Jiangtao Pei et al., 2019). As computer and communication technology advance quickly, the damage caused by DDoS attacks is becoming increasingly severe. As a result, the study of DDoS attack detection gains significance. These days, some relevant study has been conducted and advancements have been achieved. However, as of yet, there hasn't been a detection technique with adequate detection accuracy because of the variety of DDoS attack tactics and the fluctuating volume of attack traffic. In light of this, this research suggests a machine learning-based DDoS assault detection strategy that consists of two steps: feature extraction and model detection. Comparing the data packages categorized using rules allows for the extraction of a significant amount of the characteristics of DDoS attack traffic during the feature extraction stage. During the model detection phase, the attack detection model is trained using the random forest technique using the extracted features as machine learning input features. The experimental findings demonstrate that the machine learning-based DDoS attack detection method that has been developed has a good detection rate for the most common DDoS attacks at the moment.

According to Tariq Emad Ali et al. (2023), recent developments in security techniques have greatly improved the capacity to recognize and counteract threats and attacks in any kind of network infrastructure, including software-defined networks (SDNs), and shield internet security architectures from a range of dangers. Among the most widely used methods for thwarting distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) assaults on any sort of network are machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL). This systematic review's goals are to find, assess, and talk about recent developments in ML/DL-based DDoS attack detection techniques for SDN networks. In order to accomplish our goal, we carried out a systematic review in which we searched for papers that, between 2018 and the start of November 2022, employed ML/DL techniques to detect DDoS attacks in SDN networks. We have made considerable use of one academic search engine (Google Scholar) and other digital libraries (including IEEE, ACM, Springer, and other digital libraries) to search the contemporary literature. The relevant literature has been examined, and the SLR results have been grouped into five categories: (i) the various DDoS attack detection methods in ML/DL approaches; (ii) the approaches, advantages, and disadvantages of the DDoS attack detection ML/DL approaches currently in use; (iii) benchmarked datasets and classes of attacks in datasets used

in the literature; (iv) the preprocessing strategies, hyperparameter values, experimental setups, and performance metrics used in the literature; and (v) promising future directions and research gaps.

Hailye Tekleselassie (2021) This study offers a revolutionary mixed learning approach for creating a fresh DDoS model that takes advantage of deep learning's flexible and extensible properties. This technique can improve DDoS detection issues and present practices. For DDoS detection, a deep learning and knowledge-graph categorization algorithm is coupled. While a classifier model is created using a deep learning algorithm, the knowledge-graph system allows for the model's flexibility and expansion. Ten-fold cross validation is used to analytically verify it using the CICIDS2017 dataset, which has 53,127 complete occurrences. The results of the experiment show that, following connecting, 99.97% of performance is recorded. It's interesting to see that fundamental DDoS detection and prevention techniques differ in key knowledge ironic learning. Therefore, it is advised that security experts integrate DDoS detection into their network and internet.

Firas Mohammed Aswad et al. (2023) The Internet of Things (IoT) has become increasingly important and helpful to daily life in many ways due to the current era's rapid rise in informatics systems technology. The availability of several devices that serve as IoT enablers, such as smartwatches, smartphones, security cameras, and smart sensors, has led to an increase in the popularity of IoT applications compared to earlier times. However, distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) assaults are one of the challenges brought on by the unsecured nature of IoT devices. IoT systems' disreputability features, such as dynamic communication between IoT devices, provide a number of security challenges. The devices' limited resources, namely their processing units and data storage, led to the dynamic communications. A lot of work has been done lately to create intelligent models that can defend IoT networks from DDoS attacks. The primary area of continuing study is creating a model that can detect legal traffic and prevent false alarms by safeguarding the network against different types of DDoS attacks. In order to create a bidirectional CNN-BiLSTM DDoS detection model, this study suggests merging three deep learning algorithms: convolutional neural network (CNN), long short-term memory (LSTM)-RNN, and recurrent neural network (RNN). In order to identify the most efficient model against DDoS attacks that can precisely detect and discriminate DDoS from legal traffic, the RNN, CNN, LSTM, and CNN-BiLSTM are tested and put into practice. To achieve more realistic detection, the intrusion detection assessment dataset (CICIDS2017) is employed. The CICIDS2017 dataset closely resembles real-world Packet Capture data and contains benign and current instances of common threats. Confusion Matrix is used to test and evaluate the four models in relation to four widely-used criteria: F-measure, accuracy, precision, and recall. With the exception of the CNN model, which achieves an accuracy of 98.82%, the models perform quite effectively, obtaining an accuracy rate of about 99.00%. With a precision of 98.90% and accuracy of 99.76%, the CNN-BiLSTM performs best.

According to Mouli Prasad J et al. (2023), Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks involve an attacker flooding a server or network with traffic from several sources,

the majority of which are compromised devices. Sensitive data could be lost and a lot of bandwidth could be wasted by these attacks. Consequently, the significance of precisely and effectively identifying DDoS attacks has grown in the past few years. Prior research has examined DDoS detection as a binary classification problem, aiming to determine whether or not a given packet of network traffic is indicative of a DDoS attack. Therefore, in order to effectively counter a DDoS attack, it is imperative to know which kind of attack is being targeted. A unique strategy to overcome this issue turns the detection problem into a multilabel classification via the use of an ensemble classifier. The suggested Ensemble Classifier combines the best algorithms from various AI and ML approaches. This technique is effective in recognizing different DDoS attacks and classifying them into relevant groups. The multilabel classification method offers a more thorough and precise detection mechanism by concurrently identifying the existence of numerous attack types. When compared to other AI and ML algorithms, the Ensemble Classifier performs better than the other algorithms in terms of accuracy and efficiency, demonstrating the success of the suggested strategy. The suggested method may efficiently identify different kinds of such attacks and increase detection accuracy by employing the top-performing algorithms. DDoS assaults must be detected and prevented because they have the potential to seriously harm networks and companies. Because the proposed Ensemble Classifier approach merges state-of-the-art algorithms and converts the detection problem into a multilabel classification, it provides a practical and efficient means of identifying different types of DDoS attacks.

According to Wade Alhalabi et al. (2023), as intelligent information systems have proliferated, so too has the threat posed by distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks. Conventional DDoS detection approaches are insufficient for the Internet of Things due to the vast number of linked devices, continuously changing network conditions, and the requirement for immediate response. In light of this, the study's objective is to review the state of the art in the field by reading pertinent publications from the Scopus database. It also provides a brief overview of DDoS and the Internet of Things while examining neural networks and how they might be used for DDoS detection. Ultimately, a model based on decision trees is created to identify DDoS attacks. The analysis identifies areas for future research and throws light on current problems and trends in this subject.

Amrish, R. et al. (2022) A cyberattack known as a Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) assault aims to overwhelm a targeted server in order to stop normal traffic on that server. Instead of serving real users, the DDoS-attacked server is still busy processing requests from the bots. These attacks are becoming more frequent and difficult to identify. This research uses a machine learning technique to distinguish between DDoS attack traffic and regular traffic. Four methods for machine learning classification are used to identify DDoS attacks. The Canadian Institute of Cyber Security's CICDDoS2019 dataset is used to test and train machine learning algorithms. The results produced by the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) outperform those of KNN, Decision Tree, and Random Forest.

According to Anjali M et al. (2023), network assaults are a serious security risk in the modern world because of how

quickly technology and the internet are developing. DoS assaults are sophisticated and challenging to defend against. Because DDoS attacks have the potential to cause major disruptions, they are considerably more dangerous. They are especially difficult since they can swiftly and suddenly destroy a victim's computer or communication capabilities. DDoS attacks are a dynamic threat that is becoming harder to identify and successfully counter. To address this menace, we have studied numerous methodologies and methods on the DDoS attack dataset i.e. dataset unique to SDNs. By applying a variety of algorithms, such as Decision Trees, Support Vector Machine, Naive Bayes, KNearest Neighbour, Multilayer Perceptron, Quadratic Discriminant, Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), Logistic Regression, XGBoost, and deep learning techniques like Deep Neural Networks (DNN), machine learning has improved DDoS detection. Accuracy criteria have been used in a thorough comparison analysis of various algorithms to assess their performance.

According to Dhairya Lunkad et al. (2020), Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks pose a serious threat to businesses that have integrated their technology with public networks. These attacks enable multiple attackers to access data or provide services to large corporations or nations. The attacks impair the availability of Web services for an indefinite amount of time, flooding the company's servers with fraudulent requests while denying requests from legitimate users. This results in financial losses due to unavailable rendered services. With the selected attributes, various machine learning models, like Navies Bayes, SVM, and proposed methods based on Navies Bayes, are developed for efficient detection of DDoS attacks. Accordingly, the aim of this paper is to demonstrate the process of detection prototype DDoS attacks using a supervised learning model by Support Vector Machines (SVM), which captures network traffic, filters HTTP headers, normalizes the data on the basis of the operational variables: rate of false positives, rate of false negatives, and rate of classification. The information is then sent to corresponding training and testing sets. Subsequently, our experimental findings demonstrate that fuzzy c-means clustering improves attack identification accuracy.

In this study, Muhammad Rusyaidi et al. (2023) conduct a systematic literature review on the use of machine learning techniques in the detection of distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks. A number of pertinent research articles were chosen, and their evaluation was predicated on how well they demonstrated the application of machine learning techniques. The researchers are focusing on the analysis, synthesis, and evaluation of several machine learning techniques for DDoS attack detection. Thus, the goal of this research is to assess several machine learning techniques for DDoS attack detection in computer networks. The Deep Neural Network (DNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) technique, the Multiple Linear Regression method, the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) with Autoencoder, the Deep learning-based method, and the LSTM with Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) method are the five categories into which these mechanisms are classified. In addition, the research methodology, parameters, and metrics are discussed, along with a number of unresolved research issues. Summaries of findings and gaps in implementing a predictable machine learning model were also examined and contrasted. Therefore, it is anticipated that the paper will help scholars

and researchers provide a workable solution for the machine learning described above in DDoS assault detection.

Tejaswini Ulemale (2022) The digitalization of today's world has led to a sharp rise in computer technology and computer networks. As more and more works transition to an online mode, several kinds of attacks are being carried out as a result of the increased network connection. Distributed Denial of Service [DDoS] attacks are among the most potent and hazardous, and they are a serious problem in computer networks. Using DDoS, the attacker targets the server in an attempt to impede regular traffic. Distributed denial of service is one of the subclasses of denial-of-service attacks. Thus, a great deal of study has been done to counteract DDoS attacks. A prominent method for preventing denial-of-service attacks involves machine learning and deep learning. Determining DDoS attacks is the primary goal.

X. Discussions

This section comparatively presents several studies along with their comparative benefits, disadvantages & summaries of ML and DL approaches based related works. Following tables present tabular summary of various ML & DL based techniques-

Table 1. Summary of previous studies using DL related techniques

Authors	Technique	Accuracy	Accuracy (%)	Used Dataset
Mohammadpour et al. [41]	CNN	IDS	99.9	NSL-KDD
Liu et al. [40]	CNN	CNN	97	KDD-99
Imamverdiyev and Abdullayeva [39]	DBM	DDoS Detection	-	NSL-KDD
Elsaedy et al. [38]	DBM	Feature Extraction		Water Distribution Plant
Farahnakian and Heikkonen [37]	DAE	IDS	96.5	KDD-Cup 99
Tang et al. [36]	RNN	IDS in SDN	89	NSL-KDD

Table 2. Summary of Previous Studies Using ML Related Techniques

Authors	Technique	Accuracy (%)	Used Dataset
Chaudhary and Shrimal	Genetic algorithm	85	Self-data
Putri et al. [34]	K-mean clustering	99.6	ISCX
Lucky et al. [33]	Decision tree	99.9	CIC 2019 & 2017
Zekri et al. [35]	Decision tree	-	Self-Data
Ye et al. [32]	SVM	95.2	-
Fadlil et al. [30]	NB	-	MITRLADUY

Additionally, DL and ML methodologies diverge significantly. The situations in which ML or DL approaches are most appropriate could be determined with the help of these points. After summarizing related works based on both ML and DL method, significant points have been identified. For instance, when the amount of data was larger, DL approaches outperformed ML techniques in terms of accuracy. The key distinctions between DL and ML are outlined in Table 5.

Table 3. Comparison Between ML & DL Related Techniques

DL	ML
Anything from a score, an element, or free text can be the output	The output is typically a numerical number, such as a score
automatically picks up classifiers and features	Various characteristics and classifiers must be tried in order to get the best results
Human effort and involvement are reduced with DL	More human engagement and effort are needed for ML
highly computational	Faster to train a model
With a large amount of data, DL exhibited good accuracy and detection rates	With little data, ML was able to attain high accuracy and detection rates
ML includes DL	A subset of AI is ML

XI. Conclusions

DDoS attacks will continue to pose the greatest threat to a wide range of large and small enterprises due to the various harms they inflict upon internet users. The domains that might rely on a human operator, lengthy computation times, and a dearth of freely accessible data. Still, a lot of areas require attention in order to identify DDoS attacks. A variety of algorithms, including Gaussian, Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, and Linear Regression, are employed in the detection of DDoS attacks. Convolution neural networks, which are used for DDoS attack detection, are another important application of deep learning. Thus, we have reviewed a number of DDoS attack detection techniques. More than 25% of internet users in 2018 used IPv6 networks, according to the internet society. As a result, IPv6 networks will be completely dependent on the internet, particularly in light of the IoT and its enormous IP requirement. This indicates that future networks' data will be larger than IPv4 networks' data. IPv6 networks are additionally quicker than IPv4 networks. DL approaches are anticipated to yield higher accuracy and detection rates in the new networks as a result of the comparison in this research. In spite of everything, ML techniques have been fully applied to the detection of DDoS attacks, and they have produced the above-mentioned excellent results. DL methods are still thought to be superior methods for handling larger amounts of data. Additionally, assaults have their own ever evolving defences against IDS. Although not on IPv6 networks, DL techniques have been employed for DDoS attack detection. The outcomes of both ML and DL strategies based on DDoS attack detection or IDS are shown in this paper's conclusion. This paper also emphasizes the clear distinctions between DL and ML methods. In future work, we extend this work by proposing new model to detect DDoS attacks for IDS.

XII. Limitations & Scope for Future Works

The main limitation of this work is the testing reliability due to the unavailability of a realistic testing platform. Future work will focus on instigating the bottleneck of IoT network systems related to the vulnerability to DDoS attacks. With respect to future research directions, our discoveries on ML/DL techniques for DDoS attack detection point towards the following paths for further study:

- Lack of actual implementation of ML/DL systems: most research focusing on analysis of these models has neglected the crucial need to evaluate the performance of these models in the real-time situations where DDoS attacks actually occur. There remains a pressing need for

ML/DL models that have been verified using real-world scenarios.

- ML/DL models rely on dynamically and frequent updating: models that can be dynamically and routinely updated in accordance with new types of attacks are a necessity due to constant and rapid changes in attack patterns, and is a crucial element in today's world of quickly developing new technologies that carry with them more sophisticated threats. However, no such DL models are available in the literature.
- Requirement for lightweight ML/DL models: lightweight models are necessary for networks such as the Internet of Things, MANETS, and wireless sensor networks, as these have limited computational power and memory and are highly susceptible to security threats. In the future, it is expected to become increasingly necessary to develop effective and portable DL models for these contexts.
- Need for appropriate datasets: the current datasets lack diversity in terms of the types of attacks and quality of the data recordings they contain, leading to biased detection systems that are unable to identify all types of attacks. It is essential to have sufficient datasets in order to ensure accurate and effective detection models.

To close, addressing these areas of research is important in order to realize significant advances in this field and bridge the gaps that currently exist in the literature.

References

- [1] Ahmed, S.; Khan, Z.A.; Mohsin, S.M.; Latif, S.; Aslam, S.; Mujlid, H.; Adil, M.; Najam, Z. (2023). Effective and Efficient DDoS Attack Detection Using Deep Learning Algorithm, Multi-Layer Perceptron. *Future Internet* 2023, 15, 76. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi15020076>
- [2] Najafimehr M, Zarifzadeh S, Mostafavi S. DDoS attacks and machine-learning-based detection methods: A survey and taxonomy. *Engineering Reports*. 2023; 5(12): e12697. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eng2.12697>
- [3] Mahmood A. Al-Shareeda, Selvakumar Manickam, Murtaja Ali Saare (2023). "DDoS attacks detection using machine learning and deep learning techniques: analysis and comparison", *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics* Vol. 12, No. 2, April 2023, pp. 930~939 Journal homepage: <http://beej.org> ISSN: 2302-9285, <https://doi.org/10.11591/eei.v12i2.4466>
- [4] Avcı İ, Koca M. Predicting DDoS Attacks Using Machine Learning Algorithms in Building Management Systems. *Electronics*. 2023; 12(19):4142. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics12194142>
- [5] Aslam, N., Srivastava, S. & Gore, M.M. A Comprehensive Analysis of Machine Learning- and Deep Learning-Based Solutions for DDoS Attack Detection in SDN. *Arab J Sci Eng* 49, 3533–3573 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-023-08075-2>
- [6] Kumari, K., Mrunalini, M. Detecting Denial of Service attacks using machine learning algorithms. *J Big Data* 9, 56 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-022-00616-0>
- [7] Sharmin Aktar, Abdullah Yasin Nur, Towards DDoS attack detection using deep learning approach, *Computers & Security*, Volume 129, 2023, 103251, ISSN 0167-4048, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2023.103251>.
- [8] Bahashwan AA, Anbar M, Manickam S, Al-Amiedy TA, Aladaileh MA, Hasbullah IH. A Systematic Literature Review on Machine Learning and Deep Learning Approaches for Detecting DDoS Attacks in Software-Defined Networking. *Sensors*. 2023; 23(9):4441. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23094441>
- [9] Devrim Akgun, Selman Hizal, Unal Cavusoglu, A new DDoS attacks intrusion detection model based on deep learning for cybersecurity, *Computers & Security*, Volume 118, 2022, 102748, ISSN 0167-4048, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2022.102748>
- [10] Abbas, S., Bouazzi, I., Ojo, S., Al Hejaili, A., Sampedro, G. A., Almadhor, A., & Gregus, M. (2024). Evaluating deep learning variants for cyber-attacks detection and multi-class classification in IoT networks. *PeerJ. Computer science*, 10, e1793. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1793>
- [11] Mittal, M., Kumar, K. & Behal, S. Deep learning approaches for detecting DDoS attacks: a systematic review. *Soft Comput* 27, 13039–13075 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-021-06608-1>
- [12] Amitha, M., & Srivenkatesh, M.. (2023). DDoS Attack Detection in Cloud Computing Using Deep Learning Algorithms. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, 11(4), 82–90. Retrieved from <https://ijisae.org/index.php/IJISAE/article/view/3456>
- [13] Yadigar Imamverdiyev and Fargana Abdullayeva. Deep Learning Method for Denial-of-Service Attack Detection Based on Restricted Boltzmann Machine. *Big Data Jun* 2018. 159-169. <http://doi.org/10.1089/big.2018.0023>
- [14] Li Xinlong, Chen Zhibin, "[Retracted] DDoS Attack Detection by Hybrid Deep Learning Methodologies", *Security and Communication Networks*, vol. 2022, Article ID 7866096, 7 pages, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/7866096>
- [15] Rao, G. S. ., & Subbarao, P. K. . (2023). A Novel Framework for Detection of DoS/DDoS Attack Using Deep Learning Techniques, and An Approach to Mitigate the Impact of DoS/DDoS attack in Network Environment. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, 12(1), 450–466. Retrieved from <https://ijisae.org/index.php/IJISAE/article/view/3919>
- [16] Tennakoon C and Fernando S (2022). Deep learning model for distributed denial of service (DDoS) detection. *International Journal of Advanced and Applied Sciences*, 9(2): 109-118, <https://doi.org/10.21833/ijaas.2022.02.012>
- [17] Wei Guo, Han Qiu, Zimian Liu, Junhu Zhu, Qingxian Wang, "GLD-Net: Deep Learning to Detect DDoS Attack via Topological and Traffic Feature Fusion", *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, vol. 2022, Article ID 4611331, 20 pages, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/4611331>
- [18] Najafimehr, M., Zarifzadeh, S. & Mostafavi, S. A hybrid machine learning approach for detecting unprecedented DDoS attacks. *J Supercomput* 78, 8106–8136 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-021-04253-x>
- [19] Jiangtao Pei, Yunli Chen, Wei Ji (2019). "A DDoS Attack Detection Method Based on Machine Learning", *IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series*, 1237 (2019) 032040 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1237/3/032040>
- [20] Ali, T.E.; Chong, Y.-W.; Manickam, S. Machine Learning Techniques to Detect a DDoS Attack in SDN: A

- Systematic Review. Appl. Sci. 2023, 13, 3183. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13053183>
- [21] Hailye Tekleselassie (2021). “A Deep Learning Approach for DDoS Attack Detection Using Supervised Learning”, MATEC Web of Conferences 348, 01012 (2021) <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/202134801012>
- [22] Aswad, F., Ahmed, A., Alhammedi, N., Khalaf, B. & Mostafa, S. (2023). Deep learning in distributed denial-of-service attacks detection method for Internet of Things networks. *Journal of Intelligent Systems*, 32(1), 20220155. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jisys-2022-0155>
- [23] Mouli Prasad J, B Rajesh Reddy, Micheal Olaolu Arowolo, Khushboo Tripathi (2023).” Novel Machine Learning model for DDoS Cyber Attacks Threat Detection”, *Journal of Data Science and Cyber Security*, ISSN: 2584-0010, Volume 1 Issue 1 June 2023
- [24] Wadee Alhalabi, Akshat Gaurav, Varsha Arya, Ikhlas Fuad Zamzami, and Rania Anwar Aboalela. 2023. Machine Learning-Based Distributed Denial of Services (DDoS) Attack Detection in Intelligent Information Systems. *Int. J. Semant. Web Inf. Syst.* 19, 1 (Jun 2023), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJSWIS.327280>
- [25] Amrisha, R., Bavapriyan, K., Gopinaath, V., Jawahar, A. & Kumar, C. V. (2022). DDoS Detection using Machine Learning Techniques. *Journal of IoT in Social, Mobile, Analytics, and Cloud*, 4(1), 24-32. <https://doi.org/10.36548/jismac.2022.1.003>
- [26] Anjali M, Smithu B S, T Saritha (2023). “Cybersecurity Threat Detection of Anomaly Based DDoS Attack Using Machine Learning”, *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, Volume: 10, Issue: 12, Dec 2023
- [27] Dhairya Lunkad, Govind Singh (2020). “DDoS Attack Detection Using Machine Learning for Network Performance Improvement”, *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, Volume 8, Issue 9 September 2020
- [28] Muhammad Rusyaidi, Sardar Jaf, Zunaidi Ibrahim; Machine learning method in detecting a distributed of service (DDoS): A systematic literature review. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 10 January 2023; 2643 (1): 040034. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0112715>
- [29] Tejaswini Ulemale (2022). “Review on Detection of DDOS Attack using Machine Learning”, *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*, Volume 10 Issue III Mar 2022
- [30] A. Fadlil, I. Riadi, and S. Aji, “Review of detection DDOS attack detection using naive bayes classifier for network forensics,” *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 140–148, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.11591/eei.v6i2.605.
- [31] R. Vijayasathy, S. V. Raghavan, and B. Ravindran, “A system approach to network modeling for DDoS detection using a Naive Bayesian classifier,” in 2011 Third International Conference on Communication Systems and Networks (COMSNETS 2011), Jan. 2011, pp. 1–10, doi: 10.1109/COMSNETS.2011.5716474.
- [32] J. Ye, X. Cheng, J. Zhu, L. Feng, and L. Song, “A DDoS attack detection method based on SVM in software defined network,” *Security and Communication Networks*, pp. 1–8, 2018, doi: 10.1155/2018/9804061.
- [33] G. Lucky, F. Jjunju, and A. Marshall, “A lightweight decision-tree algorithm for detecting DDoS flooding attacks,” in 2020 IEEE 20th International Conference on Software Quality, Reliability and Security Companion (QRS-C), Dec. 2020, pp. 382–389, doi: 10.1109/QRS-C51114.2020.00072.
- [34] N. A. Putri, D. Stiawan, A. Heryanto, T. W. Septian, L. Siregar, and R. Budiarto, “Denial of service attack visualization with clustering using K-means algorithm,” in 2017 International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (ICECOS), Aug. 2017, pp. 177–183, doi: 10.1109/ICECOS.2017.8167129.
- [35] M. Zekri, S. El Kafhali, N. Aboutabit, and Y. Saadi, “DDoS attack detection using machine learning techniques in cloud computing environments,” in 2017 3rd International Conference of Cloud Computing Technologies and Applications (CloudTech), Oct. 2017, pp. 1–7, doi: 10.1109/CloudTech.2017.8284731.
- [36] T. A. Tang, L. Mhamdi, D. McLernon, S. A. R. Zaidi, and M. Ghogho, “Deep recurrent neural network for intrusion detection in SDN-based networks,” in 2018 4th IEEE Conference on Network Softwarization and Workshops (NetSoft), Jun. 2018, pp. 202–206, doi: 10.1109/NETSOFT.2018.8460090.
- [37] F. Farahnakian and J. Heikkonen, “A deep auto-encoder based approach for intrusion detection system,” in 2018 20th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT), Feb. 2018, pp. 178–183, doi: 10.23919/ICACT.2018.8323687.
- [38] A. Elsaedy, K. S. Munasinghe, D. Sharma, and A. Jamalipour, “Intrusion detection in smart cities using restricted boltzmann machines,” *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 135, pp. 76–83, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jnca.2019.02.026.
- [39] Y. Imamverdiyev and F. Abdullayeva, “Deep learning method for denial-of-service attack detection based on restricted Boltzmann machine,” *Big Data*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 159–169, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1089/big.2018.0023.
- [40] Y. Liu, S. Liu, and X. Zhao, “Intrusion detection algorithm based on convolutional neural network,” *DEStech Transactions on Engineering and Technology Research*, vol. 37, no. 12, pp. 1271–1275, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.12783/dtetr/iceta2017/19916.
- [41] L. Mohammadpour, T. C. Ling, C. S. Liew, and C. Y. Chong, “A convolutional neural network for network intrusion detection system,” in *Proceedings of the Asia-Pacific Advanced Network*, 2018, pp. 50–55.